

MECHANICAL BEHAVIOR OF THE HYBRID COMPOSITE SYSTEM : POLYESTER MATRIX/GLASS AND JUTE FIBERS

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Hybrid composites consisting of unsaturated polyester resin matrix and glass and jute fibers were fabricated. Different fiber volume fractions and two different arrangements of layers, viz., glass, jute, glass (GJG) and jute, glass, jute (JGJ), were used.

The modulus and the strength of composites (in tension as well as in flexure) increased with increasing fiber volume fractions. No great difference was observed in the behavior of the two types of composites when tested in tension. But in flexure, the superior performance of glass, jute, glass composites was a marked one, indicating the importance of a proper choice of the location of the various fiber species. A simple economic evaluation showed that the GJG composites had the least cost per unit specific property under flexure conditions. This behavior is as one would expect inasmuch as a body under flexure has a distribution of stresses that varies along its transverse section in a triangular form, with a maximum stress in the outermost layers and zero along the neutral axis. Thus, putting glass fibers (stronger but more expensive than jute fibers) in the outermost layers and the jute fibers in the middle would lead to a superior mechanical behavior.

INTRODUCTION

Currently, glass fiber reinforced resin composites are being used in a vast variety of fields with satisfactory results. In Brazil, however, there exists a large production of a variety of vegetable fibers such as sisal, jute, malva etc. which are used almost exclusively for making sacks, cords and other artesan products. We have an on going research program in our Institute (1-3) seeking better uses of these fibers, principally by means of substitution of the expensive glass fibers by much cheaper and abundantly available vegetable fibers in applications where the objects are not highly stressed. The earlier work (1-3) showed that mechanical properties improved, almost in a linear manner, with jute and sisal fiber volume fractions.

The objective of work reported here was to study the microstructural characteristics and the mechanical behavior of the hybrid composite system: glass and jute fibers in an unsaturated polyester resin matrix. Our study was based on one of the most important characteristics of hybrid composites, viz., the possibility to produce a cheap product by a judicious selection and distribution of the reinforcing fibers in a given matrix.

EXPERIMENTAL

The as received jute fibers were washed with a detergent to remove any grease, emulsifiers etc. on the fiber surface before testing and incorporating in resin.

Hybrid unidirectional composites, in sheet form, of glass and jute fibers in an unsaturated polyester matrix were fabricated by the leaky mould technique. A ratio of $V_j = 3 V_g$ was maintained, where V_j and V_g are jute and glass fiber volume fractions, respectively. Two types of fiber arrangements were used:

- a) Jute-Glass-Jute (JGJ)
- b) Glass-Jute-Glass (GJG)

Rectangular longitudinal test samples were cut from these sheets (i.e. fiber axis coincided with the sample axis) for the tensile tests and the three point bend test. The tensile tests were conducted in an Instron machine (100 kN capacity) while the flexure tests were conducted in an Amsler machine (6 kN capacity).

Both type of fibers were tested in tension using the card board method described in refs. (1) and (2).

The fiber volume fractions were evaluated by optical microscopy using the point counting method. A scanning electron microscope (JEOL JSM-U3), operating at between 10-15 kV and in the secondary mode, was used to study the fracture surfaces. The fracture surfaces were sputter-coated with gold to minimise the charging problem.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

MICROSTRUCTURE

A typical microstructure of the hybrid composite is shown in Fig.1. One notes the different cross-sectional forms of glass fiber (circular) and jute fiber (polygonal). The polygonal structure of jute fiber is, in fact, a multicellular structure composed of microfibrils.

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

The mechanical properties of fibers are summarized in Table 1.

The variation in elastic modulus and the ultimate tensile strength of the two types of composites as a function of the fiber

volume fraction is shown in Figs.2(a) and (b). One notes that the mechanical behavior in tension of the two types of composites (GJG and JGJ) is practically indistinguishable. They both increase linearly with V_f .

Table 1: Mechanical properties of fibers (2,3)

Fiber	σ_{max} (MPa)	E (GPa)	e* (%)
glass	1253.4	60.2	2.3
jute	270.5	21.8	1.3

* strain to fracture in 100 mm long fiber.

Fig.1 - Microstructure of the composite. Glass fibers have a circular cross-section while jute fibers have a polygonal one.

a

b

Fig.2 - Elastic modulus (a) and ultimate tensile strength (b) of the two types of composites ($V_j = 3 V_g$) showing that the two are virtually indistinguishable in tension.

The behavior in flexure, shown in Fig.3(a) and (b), is in marked contrast to that in tension. One notes that although both JGJ and GJG show increasing modulus and maximum strength with V_f , the former is by far superior to latter. This superior behavior of GJG type hybrid composites under flexure is explained by the simple theory of elastic bending of a beam, according to which the stress σ varies

a

b

Fig.3 - Apparent elastic modulus (a) and maximum strength (b) vs. fiber volume fraction ($V_j = 3 V_g$) in flexure. Notice the marked superiority of GJG over JGJ.

Fig.4 - Variation of stress long a beam cross-section in flexure.

with distance, y , from the neutral axis as

$$\sigma = \frac{M}{I} y$$

where M is the bending moment and I is the first moment of inertia. Fig.4 shows the variation of stress along a beam cross section as a function of the distance from the neutral axis. As the material in the vicinity of the neutral axis is subjected to relatively low stresses compared with the areas most removed from the neutral axis, putting in, low strength jute fibers in the central part and high strength glass fibers in the outer most layers gives the most efficient stacking sequence for conditions of flexure. In the case of tensile test, the whole of the section is subjected to the same force and, thus, one does not see any difference between JGJ and GJG types of composites.

FRACTURE

Two types of fracture modes were observed in these composites: interlaminar fracture and transverse fracture. The former was commonly observed in the glass fiber layers while the latter was associated with the jute fibers. This was especially true for low V_f composites. An example of a GJG composite (side view) in flexure is shown in Fig.5. Notice the interlaminar fracture in the

external glass fiber layers while in the central portion there has occurred a transverse fracture. In higher V_f composites ($V_f > 25\%$), the fracture surface showed a markedly higher amount of fiber pull out and interlaminar fracture. Fig.6(a) shows a scanning electron micrograph from the glass layer showing fiber pull out while Fig.6(b) shows the transverse fracture with little fiber pull out in jute layers.

It had been observed earlier (3) that jute fiber/polyester composites showed a transverse fracture with little fiber pull out. This is attributable more to the rather low strain to fracture of jute fiber than any inherent superior adhesion between polyester and jute fibers. It would appear that this fracture behavior of jute/polyester is maintained in these hybrids. The increase in the incidence of fiber pull out and interlaminar fracture at high V_f 's is perhaps due to lack of proper penetration of fibers by resin at high V_f 's.

Thus, one can say that, the fracture behavior in hybrid composites was the same as that observed in simple composites (2,3).

ECONOMIC ASPECTS

Currently, in Brazil, the ratio of unit price of glass to jute fibers is about 8 to 1. In the appendix we define parameters α , β , γ and δ with a view to make a comparison of the material costs for the GJG and JGJ for a unit specific mechanical property requirement. The smaller the value of these parameters, the cheaper is the material for a unit specific property (i.e., property/density). In the case of specific tensile strength and modulus, it is appropriate to compare the hybrid composites with plain glass fiber composites. One finds that GJG (or JGJ, as in tension the two are practically indistinguishable) becomes cheaper than plain glass fiber composites for V_f 's greater than 44% and 30%, respectively (Figs.7(a) and (b)). However, in the case of flexure, GJG is more economical than JGJ or glass fiber composites for all V_f 's (Fig.8). The curve for glass fibers composites is not shown but it lies below the JGJ curve. The same trend is observed for modulus in flexure.

CONCLUSIONS

Hybrid composites consisting of jute and glass fibers in an unsaturated polyester matrix were prepared and tested in tension and flexure. From the results of the mechanical tests one concludes that in tension the stacking sequence of glass and jute fibers is immaterial while in flexure the glass, jute, glass sequence is by far superior to jute, glass, jute fibers. This is explained in terms of stress distribution in the sample in tension and in flexure.

A simple economic analysis of the material cost per unit specific property also indicates the superiority of glass-jute-glass sequence over that of jute-glass-jute sequence.

REFERENCES

1. CHAWLA, K.K., Proc. 2nd Intl.Conf.Mech.Behavior of Materials, Boston, Aug., 1977, ASM, p.1920.
2. CHAWLA, K.K., AVILLEZ, R.R., RODRIGUES, R.R., SÁ, A.C.M., and CAVADAS, L.G.P.L., Rev.Bras.Tec., vol.9, 1978, pp. 79-99.
3. CHAWLA, K.K. and BASTOS, A.C., Mech.Behavior of Materials, Proc. 3rd Intl.Conf.Mech.Behavior of Materials, Cambridge, Aug. 1979, Pergamon Press, 1979.

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Fig.5 - Macroscopic fracture appearance in a GJG composite in flexure: interlaminar fracture in external glass layers and transverse fracture in central jute layers.

a

b

Fig.6 - Scanning electron micrograph of the fracture surface in a GJG composite, (a) glass layers (fiber pull out) (b) jute layers (transverse fracture).

a

b

Fig. 7 - Cost per unit specific property vs. fiber volume fraction ($V_j = 3 V_g$) in tension, (a) specific tensile strength, α and (b) specific modulus, β .

Fig.8 - Cost per unit specific strength, β vs. fiber volume fraction ($V_j = 3 V_g$) in flexure.

APPENDIX

We use the following nomenclature

Q - maximum load that the composite should support

X_c - price per kg of the composite

ρ_c - density of the composite

E_c - modulus in tension

σ_c - maximum stress in tension

E_c^i - modulus in flexure

σ_c^i - maximum stress in flexure

Then, cost per unit length, p , is given by

$$p = A \cdot \rho_c \cdot X_c$$

where A is the cross-sectional area.

Considering tensile strength first, we can write

$$Q = \sigma_c \cdot A$$

and defining the specific tensile strength

$$\sigma_{c,sp} = \frac{\sigma_c}{\rho_c}$$

we can write

$$\begin{aligned} p &= \left(\frac{\sigma_c}{\sigma_{c,sp}} \right) A \cdot \rho_c \cdot X_c \\ &= \frac{Q \cdot X_c}{\sigma_{c,sp}} = Q\alpha \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\alpha = \frac{X_c}{\sigma_{c,sp}}$$

i.e., price per kg per unit specific property. Similarly for tensile modulus we can define a parameter

$$\beta = \frac{X_c}{E_{c,sp}}$$

For flexure also, we can define for the maximum stress

$$\gamma = \frac{X_c}{\sigma_{c,sp}}$$

One may define, similarly, a parameter for δ for the specific modulus in flexure.

X_c , the unit price of composite, and ρ_c , the composite density were computed using the "rule-of-mixtures". Thus,

$$X_c = X_g V_g \frac{\rho_g}{\rho_c} + X_j V_j \frac{\rho_j}{\rho_c} + X_m V_m \frac{\rho_m}{\rho_c}$$

$$\rho_c = V_g \rho_g + V_j \rho_j + V_m \rho_m$$

where V is the volume fraction of a component and the subscripts g , j and m indicate glass, jute and matrix, respectively.

One must emphasize that this analysis takes into account only and only the material cost. No account is made for operational costs.